

unica4eu

A unique European vision for Artificial Intelligence to fight Childhood Cancer

The facts

Childhood Cancer represents the leading cause of death from disease for children and teenagers in Europe

35,000

children diagnosed
every year

100

different cancer
types

500,000

young survivors in
the EU

Our vision

A one-stop portal to host and curate resources and insights on Childhood Cancer and expand the uptake of clinical AI applications

Unlocking the
potential of AI

A unique
access point

One engaged
community

Visit our website

Join us in the fight against **Childhood Cancer!**

Funded by
the European Union

